

An Evaluation of the ELT Coursebooks Used in International Schools in Istanbul concerning the CLT Principles

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Abstract: Communicative Language Teaching has been a major interest of research in foreign language teaching and learning since the 1990s. This way of teaching has been very effective for language teaching and learning. Therefore, course book writers have recently published course books, considering the principles of communicative language teaching. Although there is much research on course book evaluation in the literature following a checklist or criteria, the issue of whether course books reflect communicative language teaching principles needs to be analysed. Therefore, the researcher aims to explore English language teachers' perceptions of course book evaluation, considering the principles of communicative language teaching. To achieve the objectives, the present study has employed a mixed-methods research design, which involves both quantitative and qualitative elements. This research has adopted data collection tools, which consist of an online questionnaire with a hundred and thirty-five participants and semi-structured interviews with ten participants. The findings indicate that most teachers show satisfaction with their course books, regarding the implementation of communicative language teaching principles. English language teachers are aware of the implementation of these principles in the course books they have chosen to use. In addition, the socio-demographic variables of age, gender, qualification and teaching experience are shown to have a slight impact on the course book selection process. However, the results indicate that it is the school administration that selects the course book; teachers are not allowed to make their choices, considering their priorities. These findings have significant implications for gaining new insight into the course book selection process in international schools. Although there is no best way to teach English, teachers should follow the principles of communicative language teaching in the language classroom to be able to meet learner needs, goals and interests. When choosing and evaluating the effectiveness of a course book, they should think about what course book will produce the best outcomes in terms of communication, interaction, fluency in four skills, skill integration, development of four skills and sub-skills, the communicative aim of a lesson and functions.

Keywords: Communicative Language Teaching, Evaluate, Implementation, Outcomes, Effectiveness, Learner Needs, Interaction.

1. INTRODUCTION

Traditional methods like the grammar-translation method (GTM), situational language teaching (SLT), audio-lingual method (ALM) and presentation, practice and production cycle (PPP) dominated language teaching and learning before the emergence of communicative language teaching (CLT). The ineffectiveness of traditional methods led researchers to challenge the methodological principles of these methods. CLT arose from a critical examination of the beliefs and practices related to traditional methods that dominated teaching English as a second or foreign language until the 1970s in most European countries (Richards & Rodgers, 2014). Since these methods failed to provide learners with opportunities to communicate in real-life situations, they were no longer thought to be adequate methods (Hossen, 2008; Richards, 2015; Benati, 2020; Richards & Rodgers, 2014).

The emergence of CLT goes back to the early 1970s. Hymes (1972) developed the concept of "communicative competence" and redefined what he meant by knowing a language. Learners needed to use the grammatical items of a language in real-life situations. As Hymes puts it, "There are rules of use without which the rules of grammar will be useless." It was Chomsky's concept of linguistic competence, which inspired Hymes to develop the idea of his communicative competence. However, Canal and Swain (1980) managed to relate communicative competence to language teaching. They grouped communicative competence into grammatical, sociolinguistic and strategic competence. Following this category, Canal (1983) added discourse competence and strategic competence.

There were many investments in the development of communicative language teaching across Europe. The Council of Europe developed the studies on the growth and expansion of CLT and got started with the design of a syllabus. To achieve this goal, they co-worked with a British linguist, Wilkins (1976), who organized a document involving all communicative functions needed by a learner of the target language. Richards and Rodgers (1986) explained that a syllabus considering learner needs and goals was well designed and Wilkins was the first to take into account learner needs, interests and goals. According to Wilkins (ibid), this syllabus was organised around notions and functions. Indeed, he pioneered the design of a notional and functional syllabus, which opened a new era in language teaching. He drew attention to the importance of communicative aims of a language lesson (Richards & Rodgers, 1986).

In the late 1970s and early 1980s, English teaching started to release from most traditional methods and the TBLT method emerged under the umbrella of CLT. Teachers and institutions had a changing positive attitude towards CLT. For example, language teachers and educational institutions quickly began to reconsider their teaching methods, curricula, and classroom resources across the world (Hymes, 1972; Canale & Swain, 1980; Widdowson, 1978). There was a shift from traditional grammar-centred instruction to communicative language teaching and as a result of this radical change, language teachers and institutions began to adopt CLT in language teaching and learning (Widdowson, 1990; Savignon, 1997). Indeed, CLT served as the foundation for a new generation of coursebooks and it quickly became universally recognized and appreciated (Richards, 2015). In the 1980s, CLT brought about the emergence of several methods. There was a methodological change towards the notion of a wide "approach" to language teaching that includes motives for studying English, diversity in the language classroom including different needs, goals, preferences, different learner roles and teacher roles (Nunan, 2003). In recent years, task-based language teaching (TBLT) and content and language-based instruction (CLIL) have been the extensions of CLT. Both of them are called the process-based methodologies because they both focus on creating classroom processes which are thought to best facilitate language learning (Nunan, 2003).

From the 1990s onwards, CLT has maintained its classic form and may be considered as defining and expressing a set of fundamental principles for English language teaching. For instance, it has assumptions that can be used in many methods and cover various sections of the teaching and learning processes. Language teaching approaches nowadays strive to represent the rich understanding of language and language learning suggested by a communicative view of language (Richards, 2006). Moreover, CLT will remain the dominant general language teaching approach for some time since its ideas are widely accepted by ELT researchers and applied linguists (Richards, 2006). CLT has recently become one of the most effective and dominating language instruction approaches across the world (Gil & Najjar, 2009). At present, a coursebook must include the principles of CLT to promote communicative competence and generate good communicators for real-life circumstances. Namely, today's language curriculum must incorporate many diverse components of communicative competence, such as language skills, content, grammar, vocabulary, and functions (Richards, 2006).

Statement of Research Problem

Coursebooks and the materials teachers use in classrooms need to be explored in many respects. Firstly, choosing a coursebook is a problem many teachers face in language teaching and learning. Many teachers and institutions choose coursebooks, following either a checklist or guidelines. In many schools, teachers cannot participate in coursebook selection, which makes it difficult for the programme to achieve success. Secondly, using a coursebook is viewed as a teaching skill. While some instructors view coursebooks as resources, others follow the coursebooks word for word and never vary the way they use them. If teachers cannot use coursebooks effectively, learners cannot be engaged in learning and they lose their motivation. Thirdly, teachers need to be aware of evaluating coursebooks before, during and after using them.

One gap in the literature is that there is so much work on coursebook evaluation in Turkey to explore whether they reflect CLT principles. However, research on the evaluation of a coursebook regarding the CLT approach in international schools in Istanbul is not available. Finally, although many present-day coursebooks reflect the features of CLT, can

English language teachers evaluate the coursebooks they use, considering the principles of CLT? Do EFL instructors know what characteristics or principles of CLT are available in their coursebooks?

Aims and Questions of the Study

The researcher aims to explore whether or not the communicative dimension of the English coursebooks is used by English language teachers at international schools in Istanbul. More specifically, the researcher's first purpose is to identify if the participants are aware of the communicative aims of the coursebook to address learners' communicative needs. The second purpose of this research is to identify how these coursebooks view four skills. Do they teach skills separately or do they integrate with one another? Is there a balance of four skills? The third purpose is to identify these teachers' ways of teaching grammar. What type of grammar practice do coursebooks include? Do they only include mechanical practice, which is meaningless? Do they include any meaningful practice? Do the coursebooks teach grammar deductively or inductively, e.g., through guided discovery? The fourth purpose is to identify the activities in the coursebooks and whether they reflect the characteristics of CLT activities. This study will address the following research questions:

1. What is the relationship between the demographic variables (age, gender, qualifications and teaching experience) and the evaluation of coursebooks regarding communicative language teaching?
2. How does the coursebook encourage communicative language use?
3. How does the coursebook approach four skills?
4. How does the coursebook teach, present and practise grammar?
5. What type of interaction does the coursebook emphasise?
6. What type of activities does the coursebook use and how motivated are they?
7. What type of materials does the coursebook use?

Statement of Rationale and Significance

This research is vital for teachers, researchers, syllabus designers and EFL instructors at international schools and experts in ELT. Firstly, this research is important to teachers as it will raise their awareness of the evaluation of a coursebook regarding CLT principles. What components of the coursebook reflect the principles of CLT? This research will also help them evaluate their teaching. In what ways does their teaching respond to learners? How responsive is their teaching? Can they meet learners' needs and goals? Secondly, syllabus designers can design a syllabus by taking into account the EFL instructors' perceptions of the coursebook or evaluation of the coursebook. Does the syllabus match the contents of the coursebooks? How do they perceive the coursebook they use? In what ways do they find it effective or ineffective? Can the teachers reflect on the CLT principles in their teaching? Thirdly, this research will help administrators evaluate the language course? Does the course appeal to learners, considering the CLT principles? Do the coursebooks encourage students to develop fluency and communication skills? Fourthly, the study provides an exciting opportunity to advance our knowledge of how communicative methodologies are supported by international schools in Istanbul. In particular, the findings should make an important contribution to the field of ELT by providing some suggestions for teachers in international schools to improve their teaching methods in classrooms. Finally, this study will help experts question the quality of teacher training or education programmes. Is the teacher education or training they get effective? Is their knowledge of methodology satisfying? Does the international school organise in-service teacher training for the staff?

2. METHODOLOGY

Setting and Participants

Participants in the online questionnaire have different qualifications and teach at a variety of levels at international schools. One hundred and thirty-five respondents have participated in the current study. The majority of the respondents are young, novice female teachers. They hold mostly BA and MA degrees.

The second group of participants consists of ten English teachers who are currently teaching the English language at international schools. They volunteer to take part in the interviews to collect detailed and in-depth data. The participants are limited to English teachers in Istanbul during the academic year 2021–2022. Interviews are conducted, including a variety of ten questions related to the topic of the research.

Among ten samples or participants, eight are female and two are male. The participants' teaching experience ranges from 2 to 19. Regarding the educational qualifications of the participants, they have different qualifications, including B.A, M.A, Ph D, TESOL and CELTA. In terms of school information, five of the participants work at a primary school and five of them work at a secondary school. As has been mentioned, this research focuses mainly on English teachers. That's why they are the target audience for this interview. This study is conducted in Istanbul and the data for this research are collected at international schools during the fall semester of 2021.

Data Collection Instruments

Given the aim of the study, a mixed-methods design is the most suitable research methodology. This design involves both quantitative and qualitative approaches. It is decided that the best tools to adopt for this research are to employ an online questionnaire and semi-structured interviews. The quantitative approach is adopted to collect data through an online questionnaire, and the qualitative approach is chosen to collect data through a semi-structured interview. Therefore, the researcher uses a mixed-methods design to reveal the teachers' opinions and accomplish the purposes of the investigation.

The Questionnaire

The first tool which is used for this research is conducting an online questionnaire for English teachers. The items of the questionnaire are adopted from Göçmen (2019). The introduction of the questionnaire aims to make the participants fully aware of the nature of the research and its purpose. The questionnaire is divided into two parts: the first part deals with the participants' demographic information. The questions in this section ask about participants' age, gender, qualifications, years of experience in teaching English, the one who chooses the coursebook, and the type of school she/he teaches at. The last question in this part requires the participant to state one or two coursebooks she/he uses. The second part consists of 25 items investigating participants' perceptions of coursebooks used in international schools regarding the principles of communicative language teaching. In this part, the questions deal with the design, content, methodology, activities, topics and materials included in the coursebook. Additionally, items in part two request information about interaction, skills, accuracy and fluency, as well as learner needs.

Moreover, for the attitude questions in part two, a Likert scale, which is the most popular scale preferred at this time is used. Questions in part two are measured with Likert scales of five-point types on ELT textbooks that are ranked as strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree and strongly disagree. Leedy and Ormrod (2015) indicate that Rensis Likert developed rating scales in the 1930s to assess people's attitudes; accordingly, they are also known as Likert scales. Griffiee (2012) determines that the function of Likert scales is to ask for information on closed items. More precisely, the Likert scale is used to evaluate an attitude, behaviour, or another important phenomenon (Leedy & Ormrod, 2015). In summary, Griffiee (2012) presents a simple example of the Likert scale: "a statement with the numbers one through five labelled something like: strongly disagree, disagree, not sure, agree and strongly agree. Respondents are requested to circle the number that corresponds with their opinion" (Griffiee, 2012, p. 141).

Semi-structured interviews

In addition to a questionnaire, interviews are regarded as another suitable instrument of data collection for this research. Accordingly, a semi-structured interview is adopted from Begum (2018). The interview data help the researcher gain in-depth information about the teachers' opinions. The purpose of the interview is to find out the teacher's perception of the aim and methodology of the coursebook, investigate whether grammatical items and four language skills are presented communicatively and examine the authenticity and interaction of the coursebook's activities. Therefore, the participants are asked ten open-ended questions.

Procedure

The researcher has followed all the necessary ethical procedures in collecting the data for this study. As quantitative data comes before qualitative data, the online questionnaire is first conducted. First of all, an email of approval is received from the thesis holder to use the questionnaire. Next, the items of the questionnaire are modified to reflect the objectives of the research. Then, the questionnaire is sent to the Istanbul Aydin University administration to get permission to conduct it. After the researcher receives the email of approval from the university administration, the questionnaire is prepared online through Google Forms. Then, many international schools (nine schools) are visited and contacted to invite them to participate in this research. The headmasters of the schools are provided with details about the research problem, purpose and procedures. Among all these schools, only four respond positively and share the questionnaire on their private platforms. In addition, the online questionnaire is made available to the participants for two months between November 11, 2021, and January 10, 2022. The data analysis is completed in March and April 2022. After conducting the

questionnaire, the Excel spreadsheet is coded and entered into the Statistical Package of Social Sciences Version 26. Pilot testing is done to check the internal reliability of the Likert scale according to Cronbach's alpha. Both descriptive and inferential statistical tests are run.

Regarding the qualitative data, a semi-structured interview is conducted. First of all, an email of approval is received from the thesis holder to use the interview questions. Next, the questions are modified to reflect the objectives of the research. Then, the interview questions are sent to the Istanbul Aydin University administration to get permission to use them. Finally, the researcher receive an email of approval from the administration of the university.

At first, ten teachers of the questionnaire respondents have agreed to participate in the interview. Then, the headmasters of the four schools give the researcher permission to conduct interviews and collect data. After that, the researcher talks to English teachers at those schools. However, some teachers are busy and uncooperative., so they postpone the interview many times. Therefore, the researcher has decided to email the interview questions to the participants after giving them details about the aims of this study. It seems that emailing the interview questions encourages the teachers to participate at any time. Conducting interviews starts on January 17, 2022, and finishes on March 3, 2022. Eventually, the data analysis is completed in April 2022.

3. FINDINGS

Demographic Variables

With respect to the number of respondents, 135 teachers working in several international schools have participated in this research. The first set of questions in the questionnaire aims to ask about the demographic information of the participants. Therefore, the demographic or background variables of the respondents can be divided into age, gender, qualifications and teaching experience. The last two questions in the first part of the teacher profile, ask the participants about the responsible party for choosing the coursebook and the type of school they teach at. The results of this section are presented below in Table 1.

TABLE 1: Sociodemographic Variables

		Frequency	Percent
Age	22-25	36	26.7
	26-29	26	19.3
	30-33	17	12.6
	34-37	17	12.6
	38-more	39	28.9
	Total	135	100.0
Gender	Female	96	71.1
	Male	39	28.9
	Total	135	100.0
Qualifications	BA	42	31.1
	M.A	50	37.0
	PhD.	12	8.9
	TESOL	11	8.1
	CELTA	6	4.4
	Other	13	9.6
	Total	134	99.3
	Missing value	1	.7
Total	135	100.0	
Teaching experience	1-3 year(s)	34	25.2
	4-6 years	38	28.1
	7-9 years	24	17.8
	10-12 years	3	2.2
	13- more	36	26.7
	Total	135	100.0
Coursebook Choice	You	29	21.5
	The administration	81	60.0
	The staff	24	17.8
	Missing value	1	.7
	Total	135	100.0
Schools	Primary school	42	31.1
	Secondary school	31	23.0
	High school	62	45.9
	Total	135	100.0

Teachers' Perceptions about the Coursebooks Regarding CLT Principles

The results of this section are presented below in Table 2. It reveals teachers' perceptions of the coursebooks used at international schools in Istanbul.

TABLE 2: The Agreement Percentage (%) of Likert Scales in the Questionnaire for Teachers

		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Total
1. The coursebook claims to be communicative in its aims.	Count	0	2	13	72	47	135
	Row N%	0.0%	1.5%	9.7%	53.7%	35.1%	100.0%
2. Specific communicative aims are indicated in connection with individual units when planning lessons.	Count	0	3	10	80	41	135
	Row N%	0.0%	2.2%	7.5%	59.7%	30.6%	100.0%
3. The syllabus of the coursebook is primarily communicative (e.g., by using communicative activities, functions, etc as its primary units).	Count	0	6	20	69	39	135
	Row N%	0.0%	4.5%	14.9%	51.5%	29.1%	100.0%
4. There is a reference to communicative methodology.	Count	0	9	29	67	29	135
	Row N%	0.0%	6.7%	21.6%	50.0%	21.6%	100.0%
5. There is evidence that the design of the coursebook is influenced by communicative considerations, such as the emphasis given to communicative activities, the use of authentic materials at an appropriate level, and realistic tasks.	Count	0	6	15	78	35	135
	Row N%	0.0%	4.5%	11.2%	58.2%	26.1%	100.0%
6. Communicative activities and texts promote the learning of communicative skills and strategies and resemble real-life communication (they are real, in terms of the real world, or realistic).	Count	0	8	18	64	44	135
	Row N%	0.0%	6.0%	13.4%	47.8%	32.8%	100.0%
7. Realistic activities promote the learning of communicative skills and strategies which are transferable to real-life communication.	Count	0	4	14	63	53	135
	Row N%	0.0%	3.0%	10.4%	47.0%	39.6%	100.0%
8. Genuine communication, such as unpredictability is present in the coursebook.	Count	2	21	44	48	19	135
	Row N%	1.5%	15.7%	32.8%	35.8%	14.2%	100.0%
9. The opportunities to express real information, feelings, opinions, etc., are available in the coursebook.	Count	1	10	16	70	37	135
	Row N%	0.7%	7.5%	11.9%	52.2%	27.6%	100.0%
10. The opportunities for learners to structure their discourse and the need to formulate and use communication strategies are present in the coursebook.	Count	0	9	27	72	26	135
	Row N%	0.0%	6.7%	20.1%	53.7%	19.4%	100.0%
11. The emphasis on cooperation between speakers in communicative interaction is present in the coursebook.	Count	0	7	23	72	32	135
	Row N%	0.0%	5.2%	17.2%	53.7%	23.9%	100.0%
12. The coursebook includes material that reflects the nature of communicative interaction.	Count	0	8	24	69	33	135
	Row N%	0.0%	6.0%	17.9%	51.5%	24.6%	100.0%

13. The materials are well contextualized, especially when teaching grammar and vocabulary.	Count	1	6	22	58	47	135
	Row N%	0.7%	4.5%	16.4%	43.3%	35.1%	100.0%
14. Material for spoken English (dialogues, roleplays, etc.) is well designed to equip learners for real-life interactions.	Count	3	9	25	62	35	135
	Row N%	2.2%	6.7%	18.7%	46.3%	26.1%	100.0%
15. You observe that learning through communicative activities promotes good relationships among learners as well as between learners and you as a teacher.	Count	0	2	13	51	68	135
	Row N%	0.0%	1.5%	9.7%	38.1%	50.7%	100.0%
16. All four skills are adequately covered, bearing in mind your course aim and syllabus requirements.	Count	2	7	21	68	36	135
	Row N%	1.5%	5.2%	15.7%	50.7%	26.9%	100.0%
17. There is material for integrated skills work.	Count	1	10	24	71	28	135
	Row N%	0.7%	7.5%	17.9%	53.0%	20.9%	100.0%
18. There is a good balance between receptive (reading and listening) and productive (speaking and writing) language skills.	Count	2	16	21	61	34	135
	Row N%	1.5%	11.9%	15.7%	45.5%	25.4%	100.0%
19. There are sufficient opportunities for students to use and practice their conversational strategies and skills.	Count	2	13	22	64	33	135
	Row N%	1.5%	9.7%	16.4%	47.8%	24.6%	100.0%
20. There is a balance between accuracy and fluency; they are both considered important.	Count	1	13	26	58	36	135
	Row N%	0.7%	9.7%	19.4%	43.3%	26.9%	100.0%
21. Classroom activities, topics, and contexts are varied, enjoyable, interesting, and fun. Activities are personalized where possible.	Count	1	7	20	63	43	135
	Row N%	0.7%	5.2%	14.9%	47.0%	32.1%	100.0%
22. You notice that teaching through communicative activities motivates and increases students' self-confidence to speak and initiate communicative events.	Count	0	2	13	56	63	135
	Row N%	0.0%	1.5%	9.7%	41.8%	47.0%	100.0%
23. The purpose of the communicative activities is clear and understandable. Then these activities encourage learners' classroom participation.	Count	1	5	15	69	44	135
	Row N%	0.7%	3.7%	11.2%	51.5%	32.8%	100.0%
24. The aims and objectives of the materials cater to and relate to the needs, wants, interests, purposes of the learners, and real-life tasks.	Count	0	7	30	69	28	135
	Row N%	0.0%	5.2%	22.4%	51.5%	20.9%	100.0%
25. The materials are appropriate and likely to be effective in helping learners acquire English.	Count	1	4	17	72	40	135
	Row N%	0.7%	3.0%	12.7%	53.7%	29.9%	100.0%

The main objective of the current study is to investigate the attitudes of English teachers towards the coursebooks used at international schools. Lip service has been paid for in Turkey in previous studies. Moreover, many debates surround the importance of communicative textbooks in learning languages. Therefore, the current thesis has the aim of exposing the type of ELT coursebooks in some schools in Turkey. The sample consists of almost two hundred English teachers in Istanbul. Questionnaires are the main method used to collect quantitative data on the research questions. The findings indicate that most teachers show satisfaction with their coursebooks regarding the implementation of CLT principles. Furthermore, the results reveal that the majority of the respondents agree that it is their school that assigns the type of

coursebook to be used. Consequently, the data of the current study suggest that ELT coursebooks need to be chosen by teachers instead of administrators. Finally, the sociodemographic variables of age, gender, qualification and teaching experience are shown to have a slight impact on ELT coursebook type and design.

4. DISCUSSION

Discussion of Findings

RQ 1: What is the relationship between the demographic variables (age, gender, qualifications and teaching experience) and evaluation of coursebooks regarding communicative language teaching?

Regarding the first variable of age, the current study reveals that the majority of the participants are 38 years old or older. They constitute (28.9%) of the sample. This means that they may be more experienced. This is followed by the age category 22–25, which represents (26.7%) and 26–29, which constitutes (19.3%) of the sample. In addition, the one-way analysis of variance shows that there is no statistically significant difference in mean scores for the teachers' coursebooks. However, young teachers have higher mean scores than older teachers in other age groups. Consequently, they are the most who agree with the items of the questionnaire and believe that their coursebooks reflect the principles of CLT. Finally, this result agrees with Ozsevik's (2010) findings. This study shows that young teachers are also the majority who respond to the study on implementing communicative language teaching in Turkey.

Concerning the second variable of gender, the data show that there are ninety-six female teachers, with a percentage of (71.1%). On the other hand, the number of male teachers is thirty-nine, with a percentage of (28.9%). It is observed that the majority of the respondents are female EFL instructors. Similarly, an independent-samples T-test reveals that more female respondents than the male ones feel that the coursebooks they use reflect the principles of CLT. These rather surprising findings should be explained. It can be noted that there is a higher level of agreement among female teachers than found in the second independent variable of male teachers. However, the independent Samples T-Test shows that there is no statistically significant difference between the groups. In conclusion, this result fills in the research gap on the relationship between the gender of the teachers and their perceptions about the coursebooks they use. In contrast to earlier findings, however, no evidence of employing the independent Samples T-Test was detected. Under such a result, further studies are necessary to investigate the relationship between the gender of the participants and their evaluation of the coursebooks.

As for the educational background of the respondents, the majority of teachers hold an MA or a BA degree. More precisely, teachers who hold MA degrees represent (37%) of the sample. This is followed by teachers who have bachelor's degrees, with a percentage of (31.1%). In the same vein, the mean scores of both BA and MA degrees are significant. They agree with the items of the questionnaire more than other qualification groups. This rather interesting result can be explained by the fact that they are the most who think that their coursebooks reflect the ideas of CLT compared to other degree holders. Again, the one-way analysis of variance reveals no statistically significant difference between qualification groups. Last but not least, the findings of the teachers' qualifications support previous research that always showed BA holders as the majority of respondents.

Relating to the teaching experience, the majority of the participants have a long teaching experience that ranges from three to thirteen years or more. However, the one-way analysis of variance shows that those with experience ranging from 4 to 9 years hold positive attitudes toward their coursebooks. Accordingly, they are the most likely to believe that their coursebooks follow CLT principles. Besides, there is no statistically significant difference in the mean scores between various experience levels. As a final point, this data is in agreement with that obtained by Al-bahbuh (2018). In terms of teaching experience, she notices some significant differences in the teachers' perceptions when they evaluate their textbooks.

As has been noted, the results have significant importance and meet the researcher's expectations. These findings build on existing evidence of the influence of the demographic variables (age, gender, qualifications and teaching experience) on the teacher's opinion. More precisely, the data support the researcher's hypothesis that there is an effect of some sociodemographic variables on the evaluation of coursebooks regarding CLT principles. Before answering the rest of the research questions, it is important to show the results of teachers' perceptions of the coursebooks regarding CLT principles. Therefore, table 2 presents teachers' points of view on the coursebooks used at international schools in Istanbul.

RQ 2: How does the coursebook encourage communicative language use?

The results of the questionnaire show that the majority of the teachers believe that their coursebooks encourage communicative language use. For example, most of the respondents agree that the coursebooks claim to be communicative in their aims. Furthermore, they think that specific communicative aims are indicated in connection with individual units when planning lessons. Most of the respondents also point out that there is evidence that the design of the coursebook is influenced by communicative considerations.

In addition, the participants of the interviews are asked two questions about communicative language use in their coursebooks. First of all, teachers respond to a question about language use and output. The overall response is very positive. All the teachers, except one, remark that the coursebooks' activities encourage the learners to use and produce the target language. In other words, by the end of each topic there's a space to use and produce the language; for instance, a space for writing and speaking. Secondly, teachers answer a question about the aspects of communicative language use. It is interesting to note that eight teachers state one or two aspects of the coursebooks that reflect CLT principles.

The present results are significant in at least two major respects. Firstly, teachers understand the communicative aims of their coursebooks. Secondly, they can recognize several aspects of CLT in the design and content of the coursebooks. Therefore, this observation may support the researcher's first purpose. It is to identify if the participants are aware of the communicative aims of the coursebook to address learners' communicative needs.

As mentioned in the literature review, the content of the coursebook should take into account many ideas related to the communicative approach. It has been suggested that the content should be communicative in its aims and uses, rich, interesting, relevant, varied, challenging, and understandable to make acquisition easier. It should also enable learners to use language creatively, hold the attention of the students and enrich or develop learners' knowledge and experiences (Tomlinson, 2014; Cunningsworth, 1995).

These findings are not very different from other studies. It can be noticed that there are similarities between the attitudes expressed by teachers in this study and those described by Toriki and Chalak (2017). They discover that CLT aims and concepts are used in most Iranian high school English coursebooks. In the same way, Toriki and Chalak evaluate coursebooks that promise to adopt CLT principles. They also indicate that minor adjustments to these English coursebooks might enhance their performance. Thus, the results contribute to a clearer understanding of the design, content and aspects of the coursebooks used at international schools.

RQ 3: How does the coursebook approach four skills?

This study indicates important findings on the question of how the coursebooks approach four skills. As an illustration, most of the teachers decide that all four skills are adequately covered, considering the course aim and syllabus requirements. Besides, a large number of the participants reveal that there is material for integrated skills work. Moreover, the majority of the respondents observe that there is a good balance between receptive skills and productive skills. Last but not least, most of the teachers demonstrate that there are sufficient opportunities for students to use and practise their conversational strategies and skills. Regarding the participants of the interview, participants are asked to illustrate whether the coursebook balances, integrates, or prioritises language skills. Seven teachers say that the coursebook integrates and balances the four language skills, with an emphasis on some skills. Other respondents argue that their coursebooks treat some language skills as more important than others.

These are encouraging findings and are related to one of the research aims. Notably, they should be taken into account when choosing a coursebook for learners to develop their language skills. Moreover, according to this data, we can infer that they meet the second purpose of this study. It is to identify how these coursebooks view four skills. Do they teach skills separately or do they integrate with one another? Is there a balance of four skills?

These results also support what is written in the review of the literature. To illustrate, several authors have shown that CLT emphasises the improvement of four macro skills. When Richards (2006) describes the features of communicative activities, he indicates the integration of four skills because they reinforce one another. Similarly, Thornbury (2006) points out that communicative language teaching focuses on integrated skills work. He thinks that the division of language skills ignores the idea that the majority of communication is interactive. For Thornbury, communication implies integrating both productive and receptive skills. Therefore, teachers should employ activities that combine receptive and productive skills with a good balance between them.

Finally, these findings mirror, to some extent, those of a previous study conducted by Göçmen (2019). She examines whether the CLT elements are implemented in the "INTERCHANGE" coursebook series. The findings reveal that most teachers and students believe that the coursebook integrates and balances four skills with communicative activities. However, teachers point out that the series lacks enough reading and authentic materials. Furthermore, the series is weak in employing writing activities.

RQ 4: How does the coursebook teach, present and practise grammar?

This research shows remarkable findings regarding how the coursebooks teach, present and practise grammar. The results of the questionnaire indicate that the majority of the participants emphasize that the materials are well contextualized when teaching and presenting grammar items. In addition, when the participants of the interview are asked about the approach to teaching grammar used in the coursebooks, half of the respondents comment that the coursebooks encourage guided discovery or an inductive approach. Besides, there are two useful cases in which participants have indicated that their coursebooks combine both deductive and inductive approaches. In contrast, three of the participants report that their coursebooks generally encourage teacher explanation or a deductive approach with some inductive parts. This means that the deductive approach is still present in some international schools' coursebooks.

Concerning the activities, the respondents are asked the following question: Is there too much mechanical practice? Does the coursebook include enough meaningful practice? Again, half of those asked point out that much focus is given to meaningful practice and less to mechanical practice. In other cases, the respondents present a new and interesting idea regarding this question. They emphasize that their coursebooks balance mechanical and meaningful practice. However, two participants indicate that their coursebooks focus much more on mechanical practice.

These findings provide us with new insights and meet one of the purposes of the study. For example, the results show that the inductive approach is predominant after decades of using grammar-first methods like GTM, ALM and PPP that support the deductive approach to teaching grammar. Additionally, it is noted that coursebooks in international schools focus on use and meaning when practising grammar rules. At last, these findings provide further relation to the third purpose of this research. It is to identify the teachers' ways of teaching grammar. What type of grammar practice do coursebooks include? Do they only include mechanical practice, which is meaningless? Do they include any meaningful practice? Do the coursebooks teach grammar deductively or inductively, e.g., through guided discovery?

Prior studies related to CLT have noted the importance of contextualization, an inductive approach and meaningful practice. According to CLT advocates, grammar teaching should be contextualised. In other words, the grammar item should be taught in a context so that learners can see how it is used. Otherwise, they can not apply or transfer it to a new context (Savignon, 2002). Indeed, CLT supports the idea that grammar should be taught inductively. Specifically, the teacher gives the students samples of language and, "through a process of guided discovery, gets them to work out the principle or rule for themselves" (Nunan, 2003, p. 158). At this point, communicative language teaching advocates this method of teaching grammar, which supports the learner to communicate effectively.

Moreover, there are two cases in which participants indicate that their coursebooks integrate both deductive and inductive approaches. This integration is confirmed by Nunan (2003). He has developed a method of integrating the inductive and deductive principles of teaching grammar. This method should be used to integrate grammar rules with situations and contexts from the outside world to facilitate learning words and sentences (Shastri, 2010). Eventually, the significant findings regarding the focus on meaningful practice are examined in previous studies. In reviewing the literature, there is a positive trend in CLT. It is moving away from the exclusive concentration on grammatical structures toward a high emphasis on meaning in language acquisition, communicative settings, or real-life conversations (Nassaji & Fotos, 2011). Accordingly, grammar teaching involves meaningful practice and using language communicatively to negotiate meaning (Shastri, 2010; Nunan, 1989; Widdowson, 1978).

These results agree with the findings of one study and disagree with another study. As an illustration, the present data support the research of Badger and Yan (2008). They conduct research in China to indicate the degree to which CLT is implemented in lessons, according to the resources used. In contrast with grammar-first methods like the grammar-translation method (GTM), or the audio-lingual method (ALM), the coursebooks are found to reflect more features of CLT in teaching grammar. On the other hand, the present data disagree to some extent with the research of Co (2014). He evaluates numerous coursebooks in Malaysia and Hong Kong to see how CLT affects grammar teaching. Co observes that the grammar exercises in the course materials continue to use the structural method, and CLT practices remain restricted.

RQ 5: What type of interaction does the coursebook emphasise?

Another important finding is about the interaction in the coursebooks. For example, most of the respondents indicate that the opportunities to express real information, feelings, opinions, etc., are available in the coursebook. In addition, a large number of participants decide that the opportunities for learners to structure their discourse and the need to formulate and use communication strategies are present in the coursebook. Furthermore, the majority of the teachers point out that the emphasis on cooperation between speakers in communicative interaction is present in the coursebook. Moreover, most of the respondents say that learning through communicative activities promotes good relationships among learners as well as between learners and the teacher. What is surprising is that only 50% of the teachers believe that genuine communication, such as unpredictability, is present in the coursebook, while the rest of the participants are neutral or disagree with this item.

Besides, the interview participants are asked about the idea of interaction. All of them point out that their coursebooks include both pair-work and group-work activities. They encourage students to interact and communicate with each other, with their group, or even with the whole class. Finally, these results have not previously been described when evaluating ELT coursebooks. More precisely, no previous research has investigated the concept of interaction in the light of CLT principles. Further work with more focus on interaction is therefore suggested.

Several reports have shown that interaction and communication are the major goals of language learning. For this reason, CLT employs meaningful interaction to develop language learners' communicative competence. Even classroom activities are planned to promote learning and communicative competence through cooperative and collaborative learning (Oxford, 1997). Furthermore, language is seen as a form of social interaction (Savignon, 2008). In conclusion, Larsen-Freeman and Anderson (2011) demonstrate the idea of interaction. For them, it fosters cooperative relationships among learners and between teachers and learners. Interaction also provides students with an opportunity to practise the negotiation of meaning.

RQ 6: What type of activities does the coursebook use and how motivated are they?

The items of the questionnaire investigate the types of activities the coursebooks use and evaluate their motivational factors and authenticity. To illustrate, the findings of this study show that most of the participants state there are communicative activities that promote the learning of communicative skills and resemble real-life communication (they are real, in terms of the real world, or realistic). Furthermore, the majority of the respondents describe classroom activities as varied, enjoyable, interesting, fun and personalized where possible. Besides, there are two important results focused on learner involvement or motivational factors in the coursebooks' activities. For example, a large number of teachers think that teaching through communicative activities motivates and increases students' confidence to speak and initiate communicative events. In addition, most of the participants observe that the purpose of the communicative activities is clear, understandable and encourages learners' classroom participation.

Regarding the respondents of the interview, they are asked what they think about the authenticity of the activities. Specifically, does the coursebook include task-based, meaningful and communicative activities like finding someone who, debating, role-playing or doing information-gap tasks? All the teachers express that the activities are task-based, meaningful and communicative.

These are remarkable findings and meet one of the purposes of research as well as agree with another study. Notably, the data contributes to a clearer understanding of the activities employed in the classroom settings of international schools. Additionally, the data is related to the fourth purpose of the study, which is to identify the activities in the coursebooks and whether they reflect the characteristics of CLT activities. Furthermore, it is encouraging to compare these results with those found by Criado and Sánchez (2009). According to their study, communicative activities are made up of about 50–80% of the materials in multiple secondary-upper-level English textbooks in Spain.

In reviewing the literature, communicative language teaching suggests some characteristics for activities in classrooms. For example, CLT advocates activities that resemble or parallel real-life communication. Nunan (1989) proposes ways of describing activities. He focuses on the authenticity of the activity and that it should be a rehearsal for the real-life world. Indeed, CLT emphasizes employing task-based and meaningful activities that are similar to authentic task behaviour, such as debating, finding someone, role-playing, or doing information gap tasks (Littlewood, 1981). To conclude, Littlewood points out that communicative activities develop learners' motivation since their main goal is to participate in communicative situations with their peers.

RQ 7: What type of materials does the coursebook use?

Another significant result is the coursebook's materials. The findings indicate that the materials take authentic interactions and learners' needs into account. For instance, most respondents reveal that the coursebook includes material that reflects the nature of communicative interaction. Similarly, a large number of teachers argue that the material for spoken English is well designed to equip learners with real-life interactions. Additionally, the majority of the participants emphasize that the materials are well contextualized. Moreover, the materials emphasize the importance of learners' needs and interests. In particular, most teachers claim that the aims and objectives of the materials cater to and relate to the needs, wants, interests, and purposes of the learners and to real-life tasks. Lastly, the majority of the respondents decide that the materials are appropriate and likely to be effective in helping learners acquire English.

A lot is found in the literature on the question of materials and CLT. Using authentic materials that are intended to prepare students for real-world interaction is a distinguishing feature of CLT. Specifically, there are different criteria for selecting materials in the communicative approach. According to Marcella (1998), authentic materials for a communicative classroom have the following characteristics:

- A. "The materials are learner-centred and cater to the needs and interests of the student.
- B. The texts place greater emphasis on the social function of communication.
- C. The texts provide practice with natural and meaningful communication.
- D. The texts enhance real-life language practice." (Marcella, 1998, p. 7).

In conclusion, these findings differ from the findings of Zohrabi et al. (2012). They analyze the materials of the English coursebook taught in an Iranian first-grade high school. Eventually, Zohrabi et al. discover that the book falls short of meeting the needs, interests and goals of Iranian learners. Although the coursebook is well designed, it does not focus on communicative or real-life interaction, which is the goal of language learning.

5. CONCLUSION**Pedagogical Implications**

The present study has several significant implications for course book writers, researchers, EFL instructors and administrators. To begin with, course book writers should include the features of CLT in the course books to meet learner needs, goals and preferences. Interaction and communication are the main goals of language learning, so they can emphasise numerous pair-work and group-work speaking activities for fluency development. They should also include a communicative aim or function in each unit, such as agreeing-disagreeing. Secondly, researchers should take into account the attitudes of teachers towards the implementation of communicative language teaching principles. Finally, EFL instructors should adopt CLT in the classrooms to succeed in teaching languages. Although there is no single perfect way to teach languages, CLT can be a good way to facilitate communication, interaction, functions, and skill integration in the classroom. They should emphasise meaning-focused input, meaning-focused output, fluency development and sub-skill development.

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